

Potentiometric Study of Nd^{3+} Chelates of Substituted Salicylhydroxamic Acids

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The interaction of Nd^{3+} ion with salicylhydroxamic acid and 5-methyl, 5-chloro, 5-bromo, 5-nitro, 4-chloro, 4-bromo and 3-chloro salicylhydroxamic acids is investigated potentiometrically by Calvin-Bjerrum titration technique at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ and ionic strength $\mu = 0.1 M (\text{NaClO}_4)$ in 50% v/v dioxane-water mixtures. Nd^{3+} forms only 1:1 chelates with these ligands. The validity of the $\log K = a pK + b$ relationship is examined for these chelates.

IN continuation with our earlier work on divalent metal ion chelates of salicylhydroxamic acid (SHA) and its substituted derivatives¹, in this paper we describe the complexation reaction of Nd^{3+} with SHA and other substituted SHAs. Seshadri² has reported the formation constants of the lanthanide complexes of SHA in 3:1 acetone-water medium. There is, however, no reference in literature on the present investigation.

Experimental

The ligands salicylhydroxamic acid (SHA), 5-methyl salicylhydroxamic acid (5- CH_3 SHA), 5-chloro salicylhydroxamic acid (5-CISHA), 5-bromo salicylhydroxamic acid (5-BrSHA), 5-nitro salicylhydroxamic acid (5- NO_2 SHA), 4-chlorosalicylhydroxamic acid (4-CISHA), 4-bromosalicylhydroxamic acid (4-BrSHA) and 3-chlorosalicylhydroxamic acid (3-CISHA) were all prepared in this laboratory by the known procedure³. Neodymium nitrate obtained from B.A.R.C., Bombay was used. Its solution was prepared in double distilled water and Nd^{3+} content of the solution was determined by EDTA titrations. E. Merck grade dioxane was purified by the procedure given by Vogel⁴. All other chemicals were of analar grade. The details regarding the instrumentations and the experimental procedure adopted in the potentiometric titrations are given in an earlier paper⁵.

Results and Discussion

The pH-meter readings (B readings) in the mixed solvent (50% v/v dioxane-water mixture) were converted into the thermodynamic values by the method given by Van Uitert and Haas⁶.

Proton-ligand stability constants: The proton-ligand formation number \bar{n}_A was calculated by the method of Irving and Rossotti⁷. We performed two sets of potentiometric titration experiments with varying concentrations of the ligands. The \bar{n}_A values were calculated for each set and the pK values were determined by following the pointwise method. The average of the pK values calculated for the two sets was taken as the pK value of the acid. The variation of the pK

values for the two sets was always less than the accuracy of the instrument.

The pK values determined in this work for SHA and substituted SHAs are given in Table 1. The agreement between our pK values for SHA and those reported in literature⁸ is excellent in the case of pK_2 but unsatisfactory for pK_1 .

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS

Temp. $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ $\mu = 0.1 M (\text{NaClO}_4)$, Medium = 50% v/v dioxane-water

Sr. no.	Name of ligand	pK_1	pK_2	$\log K_1$
1.	SHA	8.83	11.48	6.26
2.	5- CH_3 SHA	9.09	11.70	6.63
3.	5-CISHA	8.14	11.34	6.04
4.	5-BrSHA	7.74	11.01	5.46
5.	5- NO_2 SHA	5.56	10.84	3.92
6.	4-CISHA	7.77	11.26	5.61
7.	4-BrSHA	7.73	11.15	5.75
8.	3-CISHA	7.38	11.38	5.12

The accuracy of the pK and $\log K_1$ values was between 0.02 to 0.04.

TABLE 2—COMPARISON OF \bar{n} experimental AND \bar{n} calculated.

Temp. $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$, $\mu = 0.1 M (\text{NaClO}_4)$, Medium = 50% v/v dioxane-water
Nd³⁺-SHA system :

pL	6.94	6.75	6.55	6.36	6.17	6.08
$\bar{n}_{\text{exptl.}}$	0.171	0.240	0.275	0.412	0.585	0.656
$\bar{n}_{\text{calcd.}}$	0.172	0.244	0.339	0.442	0.551	0.602

Standard deviation = 0.04.

Nd³⁺-5-CISHA system :

pL	6.64	6.45	6.25	6.06	5.97	5.89
$\bar{n}_{\text{calcd.}}$	0.200	0.280	0.381	0.488	0.540	0.685
$\bar{n}_{\text{exptl.}}$	0.171	0.240	0.309	0.378	0.550	0.756

Standard deviation = 0.07.

Literature survey reveals that the keto form is predominant in solution in the case of SHA and substituted SHAs⁹. The keto form has three dissociable hydrogen atoms viz. -NH, phenolic -OH and -N.OH. Chemists differ in assigning the pK values in SHA to the dissociations of the proper functional groups. Kabadi et al⁹ have ascribed the lower pK value to the dissociation of the phenolic -OH and the other pK value to the dissociation of the -N.OH group. They have, however, not considered the possibility of the -NH dissociation, even though they have given the pK value for proton affinity of the nitrogen. Exner and Kakac¹⁰ report that it is the hydrogen bound to the nitrogen that dissociates first. Dutt and Seshadri¹¹ have given two pK values for SHA, the higher one they have ascribed to the dissociation of the phenolic -OH. In our studies, we report two pK values. The pK_1 value we ascribe to the dissociation of the -NH group and the pK_2 to the dissociation of the phenolic -OH. We feel that the -N.OH group being the most basic one does not dissociate even when the B reading is 12.0 and its pK value could not be determined because of the limited accuracy of the instrument in the B region above 12.0. We justify our assumptions by the following arguments :

(i) The pK value of phenol was determined by us in 50% v/v dioxane-water mixture and at 0.1 M (NaClO_4) ionic strength. The value came out to be 12.0. If it is assumed that the phenolic -OH group in SHA dissociates prior to the -NH group, then a reduction in the pK value to the extent of 3.17 pK units should be ascribed to the effect of the hydroxamic acid group on the phenolic -OH group. Such a possibility seems to be remote. If pK_2 is ascribed to the dissociation of the phenolic -OH group, then the reduction in the pK value to the extent of 0.52 pK unit can be thought to be due to the hydroxamic acid group. This leads to the conclusion that pK_1 is due to the -NH dissociation.

(ii) The pK values for phenolic dissociations in *o*-hydroxy acetophenone and *o*-hydroxy acetophenone oxime in 75% v/v dioxane-water mixture are 14.0 and 13.76 respectively¹². Similarly the pK value of phenol and pK_2 of SHA in the same percentage of dioxane-water mixture are 14.20 and 13.62 respectively. These data show the reduction in the pK value of the phenolic -OH due to the presence of the hydroxamic acid group should be around 0.2 to 0.6 pK unit. The pK_2 value of 11.48 in the case of SHA should, therefore, be ascribed to the phenolic -OH as the pK value of phenol is 12.0.

(iii) The parent ligand was acetylated so that the -N.OH group was converted into N.OCOCH_3 . The pK value of this acetylated compound was determined in 50% v/v dioxane-water mixture. The pK_1 value observed was 5.8. The reduction in pK_1 value to the extent of three pK units was thus observed. The acetal group can have such a pronounced effect only on the -NH group and not on the phenolic -OH group. The pK_1 must, therefore, be ascribed to the dissociation of the -NH group and pK_2 to the dissociation of the phenolic -OH group.

Metal-ligand stability constants: The deviation of the metal complex titration curve from the reagent titration curve commenced around B 4.5 and the precipitation was observed around B value 5.5. The metal-ligand formation number \bar{n} in this B range gave an indication of the formation of only 1 : 1 complexes. For the estimation of the $\log K_1$ values, the pL values were calculated by the formula :

$$pL = \log \frac{1 + H/K_1}{T^{\circ}_L - \bar{n} T^{\circ}_M} \cdot \frac{V_0 + v_3}{V_0}$$

where T°_L and T°_M are the stoichiometric concentrations of the ligand and the metal ion respectively, V_0 is the initial volume of the solution and v_3 is the volume at a particular B reading in the acid + ligand + metal titration. The $\log K_1$ values were calculated with the help of the expression :

$$\log \frac{\bar{n}}{1 - \bar{n}} = \log K_1 - pL$$

This expression was solved by the graphical relation in the plots of $\log \frac{\bar{n}}{1 - \bar{n}}$ vs pL . The values of \bar{n} selected

were in the range 0.2 to 0.8. The number of readings in each case was 5 to 6 and all the points fell on a straight line whose correlation coefficient was very close to 1.0 in each case. The accurate values of $\log K_1$ were determined by the method of least squares. The $\log K_1$ values thus calculated were utilized to get the theoretical formation curve. A representative data is given in Table 2. The agreement between the theoretical and the experimental values is good over the entire B range.

The final $\log K_1$ values determined in this work are given in Table 1. Earlier we have reported the formation constants of the transition metal ion chelates of these SHAs¹ and have discussed the significance of $d\pi - p\pi$ interaction in these chelates. In the case of lanthanides, the 4f orbitals are effectively shielded from interaction with ligand orbitals by electrons in the 5s and 5p orbitals. If hybridization is to occur, it must involve the normally unoccupied higher energy orbitals (e.g. 5d, 6s, 6p) and hybridization of this type can be expected with the most strongly coordinating ligands. Rare earths, therefore, normally form ionic compounds. The type of complexation in the present case was judged by comparing the slope values of $\log K$ vs. pK plots obtained for the Nd^{3+} chelates and those of transition metal ion chelates. The plot of $\log K_1$ vs. pK_1 for the Nd^{3+} chelates gave a very satisfactory linear plot with a slope 0.85. Jones et al.¹³ suggest on the basis of a purely electrostatic model that the slope will increase with increasing cationic charge and decreasing distance of separation (equal to radius of the cation + constant). In the case Nd^{3+} chelates of substituted SHAs, the slope value is nearly the same as that obtained for the transition metal ion chelates. Though the higher charge on rare earth cations is expected to give a higher value for the slope than that for the transition metal ion complexes, the observed lower value may be explained as due to the higher values of cationic radii in the case of rare

earths. The distance of separation between the cation and the ligand is also expected to be greater in the case of the rare earth complexes because of the ionic nature of these complexes as compared to the transition metal ion complexes.

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